

Research and Innovation

September 2023

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context and progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find a first outline of the baseline data collected during 2022 and the first months of 2023.

In terms of Research and Innovation, the monitoring focuses, on the one hand, on the context indicator “Summary Innovation Index” and, on the other hand, on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see on the backside of this document).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Summary Innovation Index

Source

European Innovation Scoreboard 2022.
EU countries and neighbouring countries database
<https://tinyurl.com/source-first>
(accessed 25 May 2023)

Note

Data for Kosovo* not available

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Priority

Boosting the WB Innovation Capacity by bringing Research and Innovation (R&I) eco-systems closer to the EU

Regional Indicators

WB Steering Platform meetings	Regional Policy Dialogue	POLICY ANSWERS launched	Evidence based policy courses
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Legend: On track or maintaining achievement | Moderately improving, Challenges remain | Stagnating, Significant challenges | Decreasing, Major challenges | Information not available

WB Economy Indicators

Performance of the WB economy: good medium to be improved information not provided

Supporting Western Balkans reforms for science & research alignment with EU acquis Participation in European programmes, initiatives and schemes				
	Technical assistance to Chapter 25 (Science and Research) reforms	Governments to increase GDP allocations to R&I	Investment in R&I and education infrastructure	Integration in the new ERA
Albania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Bilateral TA projects Guidelines produced - Low level of Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes fully absorbed - Low %GDP dedicated to R&I 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes in place, fully absorbed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Horizon Europe association Joint projects & mobilities Progress in the ERA integration
Bosnia and Herzegovina	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Bilateral TA projects Increased alignment with EU Acquis - Guidelines produced Low level of Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes fully absorbed - Low %GDP dedicated to R&I 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes in place, fully absorbed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Joint projects & mobilities Progress in the ERA integration
Kosovo*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Guidelines produced - Low level of bilateral TA projects and Twinning projects Low uptake of TAIEX missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes in place - Low %GDP dedicated to R&I Absorption level not specified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No dedicated funding scheme(s) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Joint projects & mobilities Progress in the ERA integration
Montenegro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Increased alignment with EU Acquis - Low uptake of TAIEX missions - Low level of Twinning projects and bilateral TA projects No guidelines produced 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes in place, almost fully absorbed - Low %GDP dedicated to R&I 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governmental funding scheme in place with rather low level of absorption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Joint projects Progress in the ERA integration - Low level of individual transnational mobilities
North Macedonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Guideline produced TAIEX missions - Low level of Twinning projects and bilateral TA projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes fully absorbed - Low %GDP dedicated to R&I 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governmental funding scheme in place, absorption level not specified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Joint projects Progress in the ERA integration - Low level of individual transnational mobilities
Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Twinning projects Bilateral TA projects Increased alignment with EU acquis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Governmental funding schemes fully absorbed - %GDP for R&I higher compared to other economies, still below EU average 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governmental funding scheme in place, absorption level not specified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Joint projects & mobilities Progress in the ERA integration

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